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THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CARDIAC SURGERY SERVICE IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF PARNAÍBA - PIAUÍ, BRAZIL

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ABSTRACT

Changes in the profile of patients with structural heart disease have been observed in recent decades, reflecting the greater longevity of the general population and the increased severity of those referred for surgical treatment, making it necessary to offer specialized services in cardiovascular surgery. Objective: To analyze the process of implementing the cardiac surgery service in the municipality of Parnaíba. Methods: This is a documentary, intervention and retrospective study with a qualitative and quantitative approach. Results: The process of receiving patients eligible for cardiac surgery before the service was set up was identified; the implementation of the cardiac surgery service in the municipality of Parnaíba was inferred; the legacy of the implementation of the cardiac surgery service in the municipality of Parnaíba was identified, as well as the subsidies needed to draw up programs for technical and professional development and improvement. Conclusion: The final responsibility for the success or failure of the surgical patient's evolution lies primarily with the act. Although some unfavourable organizational factors are often beyond the scope of this procedure, these factors undoubtedly play an important role. In view of these peculiarities, there is a perennial need for everyone's involvement, especially with regard to monitoring surgical results, demanding better working conditions and investing in professional training and research applied to daily practice.